

Local Environment

The International Journal of Justice and Sustainability

ISSN: (Print) (Online) Journal homepage: www.tandfonline.com/journals/cloe20

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To cite this article: Bokolo Anthony Jnr (09 Nov 2024): Exploring mobility equity, equality, and accessibility for older people in the local environment: a systematic literature review, Local Environment, DOI: [10.1080/13549839.2024.2424437](https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2024.2424437)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2024.2424437>

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Published online: 09 Nov 2024.

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Exploring mobility equity, equality, and accessibility for older people in the local environment: a systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

People above 65 years of age, are confronted with several issues that limit them from fully participating in society and exercising their rights to accessing the local environment. But older people's ability to travel independently and freely to participate in society is crucial for their quality of life. The question of how to maintain mobility equity and equality for older people is, however, a complex one. This is because older people, especially those with disabilities, are often faced with mobility exclusion due to physical barriers around the public transportation and built environment. This has been further intensified as existing mobility accessibility initiatives employed by municipalities have not involved vulnerable groups in society such as older people. Therefore, this study adopts a systematic literature review based on data collected from 83 sources indexed in Scopus and Web of Science database. The findings from this article present factors that influence the local environment in achieving mobility equity and equality from the perspectives of older people, living without and with disabilities. Evidence from this study proposes guidelines grounded on a universal design framework to help municipalities foster mobility equity and equality for older people based on recommendations provided to inform urban transport policies on universal accessibility.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 8 August 2023
Accepted 27 September 2024

KEYWORDS

: Mobility equity and equality; older people; mobility accessibility; public transportation; urban mobility policies; local environment

1. Introduction

In urban transportation, mobility is often associated with locomotion or movement and is measured as out-of-home journeys or trips. The mobility or the ability of older people to carry out daily trips is important in accessing goods and services (Siren, Hjorthol, and Levin 2015). Mobility is fundamental for participation in society and promotes the functional capacity, autonomy and health of older people (Levin et al. 2012; Mackett 2020). Mobility is thus a necessary human need and a requirement for a self-determined and independent life, as well as a necessity for achieving equitable and equal participation in society (Zimmermann-Janschitz, Mandl, and Dückelmann 2017). For this reason, older people with disabilities are often socially excluded, thus some are not able to travel daily. Improving mobility availability and accessibility can help improve the lives of older people from one of dependency and exclusion to one of social integration and independence (United Nations 2007). In Europe, the number of inhabitants aged 65 years or over in the total population is predicted to increase from 17 per cent in 2008–30 per cent in 2060 (Eurostat 2008). In the Scandinavian

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countries (Sweden, Norway and Denmark), the percentage of persons 65+ years of age is predictable to increase to 25 per cent in 2060 (Eurostat 2008). Travel trends and patterns in society have substantially increased over the last decade, but remarkably so for older people. As such, the travels made by older adults have increased (during 1985/1986–1996/1998) by almost 12.2 per cent to 18.8 per cent, respectively (Banister and Bowling 2004).

Furthermore, the findings from prior studies revealed that most countries are confronted with the provision of public transportation systems that offer equal access and equitable mobility for older people with difficulties in walking, travelling and using public transportation or driving (Hjorthol 2013; OECD 2001). To ensure equal and equitable opportunities, it is also important to promote inclusive mobility for older people and those living with disability (WHO 2014, 2018). But older people are faced with barriers in the built environment and public transportation infrastructure, such as poorly built public vehicles and road systems, insecure and unsafe services, lack of wayfinding and walkability aids, reduced accessible transportation options, reduced prospects for meaningful participation within the society and undesirable attitudes of the general public (Bokolo, Petersen, and Helfert 2022; Tennakoon et al. 2020). But with numerous individuals aged over 65, municipalities need to start focusing more closely on understanding older people's mobility accessibility needs, to ensure that explicit requirements are not being unnoticed (Banister and Bowling 2004; Salmela, Popova, and Kiviluoto 2020). This particularity will help to understand the different needs of older people, identifying facilities and services that can better cater to these vulnerable groups in society (Peraković, Periša, and Bilić Prčić 2015; Zimmermann-Janschitz, Mandl, and Dückelmann 2017).

The findings from the literature show that the quality standards of existing public transportation do not adequately provide safety for older passengers even though public transportation modes are supposed to provide a safe mode of commuting. Older people, mostly those who are with disabilities, are often frail and are prone to sustaining injuries (Lahav 2014). Likewise, over the decade, several policies and strategies have been put forward by the European Union (EU) to improve mobility accessibility in public transportation systems, especially for older people with disabilities (physical, in a wheelchair or with legal blindness/vision impairment, sensory and learning impairment) (Sze and Christensen 2017). Many cities in the EU propose and initiate sustainable public transportation systems. Unfortunately, older people often are hesitant towards these mobility alternatives as their specific needs are not well considered. Besides, given the heterogeneity of the older population (65–74 and 75 and older), a variety of mobility accessibility options (for disabled and non-disabled), will be desirable (Levin et al. 2012). Moreover, older passengers with functional limitations mostly rely on accessible public transportation for commuting and social participation. Thus, safe mobility measures for these groups need to be considered to improve the welfare and well-being of older people for societal integration (Marin-Lamellet-INRETS and Simoes-ISEC 2010). The literature that explored how to fulfil the transport needs of older people is limited (Zimmermann-Janschitz, Mandl, and Dückelmann 2017). It is crucial to review the current practices and guidelines governing the planning and design of public transportation facilities provided by municipalities that could impact the travel behaviour of older people, especially those with disabilities. As such, there is a need to investigate how to address the unmet transport needs of older about balancing mobility equity and equality for older people (Sze and Christensen 2017). Therefore, this study aims to investigate the following research questions.

- What are the existing works related to mobility equity and equality for older people in the local environment?
- How can universal design measures help to promote mobility equity and equality for inclusive transport systems for older people?
- What factors influence older people's mobility, especially those with disabilities in the local environment?

To address the above research questions, the goal of this study is to provide *good practice* schemes, policy recommendations and guidelines grounded on universal design to balance mobility

equity and equality for older people. Also, this study takes a close look at the state-of-the-art on mobility patterns, needs and requirements of older people over 65, individualising between the “young-elderly” (aged 65–75 years) and the “older-elderly” (over 75 years) (Levin et al. 2012). In this article, appropriate design strategies for the walkway environment (e.g. pedestrian, accessible route, crossing footpath, curb, and ramp, etc.) and/or access to public transportation facilities (e.g. transport vehicles, stairs, lift, movable walkway, escalator, platform, etc.) are specified. Thus, the findings from this study identify the appropriate design of public transportation facilities and services which will enable accessible for all, including older adults and those with disabilities. More importantly, the findings will promote the awareness of legislation, policy and procedures needed for mobility equity, equality and accessibility needs. Overall, this article is organised as follows: Section 2 presents related works; Section 3 defines the methodology; Section 4 describes the findings; Section 5 is the discussion and main implications; finally, Section 6 describes the conclusion of the study.

2. Related works

Over a decade, a few studies have contributed to the mobility of older people. Hanson, Goudreau, and Copp (2020) presented a community-based method for addressing transport needs for rural older adults across Canada. Mackett (2020) researched ways of addressing mobility barriers that affect the access for older people to enable them to travel more. Tennakoon et al. (2020) studied transport equity for disability and older people in Sri Lanka. Tanaka (2018) researched the use of new technologies for personal mobility and assistive devices such as robot suits mainly for the elderly and persons with disabilities. Eisenberg et al. (2017) researched how to plan the walking environments for older adults and people with disabilities. Vanderschuren, Baufeldt, and Phayane (2015) investigated mobility barriers for older persons based on the universal design needs across South Africa. Hjorthol (2013) explored mobility, transport resources and unmet transport needs faced by the older population. Levin et al. (2012) presented measures as best practices to improve mobility among older people in Norway, Sweden and Denmark. Titheridge, Mackett, and Achuthan (2010) compared transport accessibility, as determined by planners, as experienced by older people and those with disabilities. Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty (2002) examined social and transport exclusion and further investigated the possibility of advancing inclusion via virtual mobility.

Although transportation accessibility to improve the mobility of older people, especially for older people with disabilities, has extensively been examined in the literature, only limited studies examined how to foster mobility equity and equality for older people and those with disabilities. Specifically, fewer studies employed universal design measures to help improve mobility inclusion for older people in the local environment. Also, there is a need to explore factors that negatively influence older people’s mobility, especially those with disabilities from a local environmental perspective. Understanding of how to improve mobility equity and equality for older people who use public transportation and when they walk within and across the local environment will assist municipalities, transport planners and urban designers in reconsidering how they re-design pedestrian/walkways and public transportation systems required by older people with disabilities to improve social inclusion of older adults (Park and Chowdhury 2022; Riggs and Sethi 2020).

3. Methodology

In this study, a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was adopted based on guidelines from Kitchenham and Charters (2007); Fink (2019) to guide this study based on a review protocol, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 shows the review protocol which comprises five activities: development of research questions, specification of search strategies, presentation of inclusion and exclusion criteria, quality assessment criteria and data extraction and synthesis. Each of these phases is discussed below.

Figure 1. Review protocol employed in this study.

3.1. Research questions

This study adopted an SLR to provide an agenda for exploring mobility equity and equality for older people in the local environment. Then universal design measures are employed to promote mobility equity and equality for inclusive urban transport systems. The following good practice schemes, policy recommendations and guidelines to be adopted to promote mobility equity and equality for older people in the local environment are presented. Overall, the research questions to be examined are presented in the introduction section of this paper.

3.2. Search strategy

A comprehensive search was carried out to identify studies related to mobility equity and equality for older people in the local environment, using online libraries from August 2022 to October 2023 in Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, ProQuest, Springer, Wiley, IEEE Xplore, Emerald, ISI Web of Science, Sage, Inderscience and Scopus, as suggested by Anthony Jnr (2022). These online databases studies, related to mobility equity and equality for older people in the local environment, were collected from journal papers, conference proceedings, book chapters and technical reports. Furthermore, in executing the search specifying keywords or search terms were used to search online electronic databases. To confirm review quality, search keywords were formulated using Boolean AND/OR operators to combine the search terms derived from prior studies Anthony Jnr 2021; (Fink 2019; Lindkvist and Melander 2022). The main search terms comprise “mobility equity”, “mobility equality”, “universal design”, “inclusive mobility”, “mobility for all”, “mobility of people with disabilities”, “mobility of older adults”, “mobility of older people” and “local environment”.

3.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

In the early stage of the search process, 194 potential studies were retrieved from the online libraries. Each collected sources were critically examined to select only sources that could provide accurate answers to the research question. Figure 2 illustrates the study selection process.

As shown in Figure 2, the retrieved 194 sources were checked for duplicates/similarities and 33 papers were removed remaining 161 sources. In the third phase, the remaining 161 sources were assessed by checking their titles and abstracts to ensure they were related to mobility equity and equality for older people and 65 sources were removed which remained 96 sources. Next, the selected papers were passed through the inclusion and exclusion criteria, as shown in Table 1.

Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 13 sources were removed and 83 relevant studies remained. The selected 83 sources included in this study comprise 34 Journal articles, 12 conference proceedings and 37 book chapters and technical reports. The sources can be seen in the reference section of this paper.

Figure 2. Study selection process.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Studies published in the English language.	Studies that are not written in the English language.
Journal articles, conference proceedings, technical reports and book chapters.	Not journal articles, conference proceedings and book chapters
Published from 2000.	Published before 2000.
Studies that provide possible discussion and implications to research questions based on title and abstract content.	Remove duplicate/similar studies by retaining the most current and comprehensive version.
Quantitative, qualitative, modelling and experimental studies that provide evidence.	Studies that do not provide any theoretical or practical evidence.
Studies related to the research questions being explored.	Studies not related to the research questions.
Studies related to mobility equity and equality for older people.	Studies not related to mobility equity and equality for older people.

3.4. Quality assessment criteria

In this phase of Quality Assessment Criteria (QAC), all included studies are either indexed in Scopus or the Web of Science database. The QAC confirms that more than 50 per cent of the included sources have been peer-reviewed and published in quality venues and top international journals and conference proceedings; as such, no source was removed.

3.5. Data extraction and synthesis

In this stage, the selected sources provided information based on issues related to mobility equity and equality for older people. First, the study proceeded to specify the mobility accessibility of older people, mobility policies, walkability and wayfinding and factors that impact older people's mobility from each source. The collected data were then structured to enable mapping across studies. The selected studies were reviewed in detail and relevant data were further extracted,

analysed and synthesised to conceptualise the universal design measures relevant to promote mobility equity and equality for older people in the local environment.

4. Findings

4.1. Background of older people's mobility

UNDESA (2017) predicted that the global population of people aged 60 years or over is projected to reach almost 2.1 billion by 2050. The availability of public transportation service to older people is of uttermost importance as it offers older people the opportunity to be fully involved in the community and also improves their quality of life (Anthony Jnr 2020; Solecka, Hoy, and Deryło 2020). Thus, mobility is important for people to actively take part in society today. For older people, the availability and accessibility to public transportation and the ability to move around are crucial from a societal and individual perspective (Bokolo, Petersen, and Helfert 2022; Mackett 2020). As such, over the years mobility accessibility measures have been proposed to be deployed (Cattaneo et al. 2022; Levin et al. 2012). According to Levin et al. (2012), urban public transport solutions are grounded in three main areas as shown in Figure 3.

As shown in Figure 3, each of the mobility options is discussed below.

- Traditional fixed route service involves standard 12-metre low-floor city buses, trams or metro-trains which support the mass mobility of persons with little or no mobility restrictions.
- Fixed routes, service routes or flexible routes on demand involve the types of mobility options that provide smaller low-floor buses which are normally operated on routes which are close to the residence of older people as well as health facilities and service centres.
- The special transport service involves dedicated mobility services, which are made available to older people who face mobility issues, are disabled and require door-to-door mobility and/or personal assistance. This mobility service is primarily operated with multi-purpose vehicles or taxis (Levin et al. 2012).

In Norway, a *specialised transportation service* is provided for older people who need door-to-door mobility service and are unable to utilise the normal public transportation system (Ruter 2017; Sparelabs 2019). This mobility service offers fewer trips and economic incentives for a given period for older people to carry out activities such as leisure activities, visiting friends and family, shopping and so on (Hjorthol 2013; Viken.no 2022). The specialised transportation service is suitable for older people with reduced mobility such as those who experience challenges when moving around the local environments and those with adapted mobility needs, such as older people with walking difficulties, limb problems, in wheelchairs, those who are legal blindness/vision impairment, deaf or hearing difficulties (Solecka, Hoy, and Deryło 2020).

Figure 3. Urban public transport solutions.

4.1.1. Mobility perspective of older people with disabilities

According to the World Health Organisation (WHO 1980), impairment is an abnormality or loss of physiological, psychological, function bodily or structure. Disability is described as any lack or restriction which results from an impairment or individual's ability to accomplish an activity in a manner that is within the range considered normal for human beings (WHO 1980). As stated by WHO (1980), disability encompasses activity limitations, impairments and participation restrictions. *In this study, the definition of disability would be adopted from the Code on Accessibility in The Built Environment*, proposed by Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty (2002) where the author mentioned that the disable refers to those people who have a consequence of impairment physical or disability. A disability may be sensory, physical, emotional, developmental, cognitive or some combination of these (Abir and Hoque 2011). According to the literature, the dimension of disabilities involves *cognitive, sensory and physical impairment* (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). Similarly, Soltani et al. (2012) highlighted that in the context of the physical urban environment, disabled people may be grouped into *wheelchair-bound, ambulant disabled, temporary disabled and sensory disabled*.

Table 2 shows the basic forms of disability faced by older people that require technological assistive devices for improving mobility. Older people with disabilities (*physical, in a wheelchair or with legal blindness/vision impairment, sensory and learning impairment*), have traditionally not been well included in public services such as public transportation (Chaurasia, Sankat, and Solanki 2017).

As such, their inability to access public transportation in the journey value chain is one of the driving influences that lead to mobility inequity and inequality for older people, especially those with disabilities (Park and Chowdhury 2022). Through social movements during the 1960s and 1970s, disability civil rights surfaced in countries such as the United States of America (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK) to advocate for human capabilities and social inclusion (Chaurasia, Sankat, and Solanki 2017). The findings from prior studies suggested that shared spaces present issues for older people with disabilities (Park and Chowdhury 2022). Access to public transportation was an important necessity of disability movements. While other countries are beginning to initiate policies on recognising the overall rights of persons with disabilities, improvements in public transportation systems such as the city bus are being implemented to shift the paradigm of urban mass transit (Chaurasia, Sankat, and Solanki 2017).

4.2. Social equity and equality for the mobility of older people

Mobility has a significant social function. It can be seen as a social service, which facilitates community participation and interaction, whether during the journey or at the destination (Anthony Jr 2024; Imrie and Hall 2003). Equity and equality relate to the provision of inclusive access to an individual or group, given the opportunity to partake in the political and social life of the community (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). Equity and equality address individuals' denial of access to opportunities, emphasising the resolving of structural constraints that limit community participation. Mobility equity and equality are influenced by mobility exclusion which refers to the process by which individuals are limited from participating in the political, economic and social life of the community due

Table 2. Basic forms of disabilities faced by older people.

Forms	Description
Sight	Partial impairments or total blindness affecting the sight of older people to the extent that their functioning in public areas is exposed to danger or insecurity.
Hearing	Hearing handicaps or deafness might make older people to be insecure in public spaces due to the person not able to hear warning signals or communicate.
Semi-Ambulatory	Impairments that cause older people to walk with insecurity or difficulty. This involves older people who uses crutches or braces. Also, individuals with amputees, spastics, arthritis and ladies with those with cardiac ills and pulmonary are in this category.
Non-Ambulatory	Impairments that, irrespective of manifestation or cause, for all practical purposes, confine older people to Wheelchairs.

to reduced accessibility to social networks, services and opportunities due, in part, to or whole to inadequate mobility services in the local environment (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002; Sommer 1983). As a consequence, older people, especially those with disabilities with inadequate mobility, can face less equality for mobility opportunities and a minimal ability to partake in civic life (Hamiduddin and Plueckhahn 2021).

A key outcome for equitable and equal mobility design should be able to attain a greater measure of social inclusion and justice. However, there have been concerns that in many cases it is not viable to provide a “one size fits all” design solution for everyone as some vulnerable groups in society will constantly be excluded (Imrie and Hall 2003; Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). Instead, there is a need to provide customised and tailored mobility infrastructures and services to address conditions where it is principally difficult to expand existing design parameters to include everyone. Actualising an equitable and equal mobility design is a complex process, which involves an integrated method deployed to address the weaknesses of traditional design approaches. However, this demands the adoption of a user-centred approach to design mobility services that involve older peoples’ mobility requirements. This has been characterised as “social design” whose main goal entails “working with people”, “not for them” (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002; Sommer 1983). Figure 4 depicts the difference between social and non-social design.

Older people are faced with different mobility obstacles and barriers (Zimmermann-Janschitz, Mandl, and Dückelmann 2017), when they walk across and within cities, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Social and non-social design principles adapted from (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002).

Figure 5. Mobility obstacles and barriers faced by older people.

To improve equitable and equal mobility access to older people, barriers in the use of public transportation need to be addressed, such as the lack of accessibility, available, affordable public transportation and inadequate training and educational opportunities and choices, for all literacy and age groups can also promote equitable and equal mobility (Imrie and Hall 2003; Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). While an improvement in the availability, accessibility, affordability and acceptability of public transportation could increase the mobility equity and equality of older people, especially for older people with disabilities, it is unlikely to design an inclusive mobility infrastructure for all (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). An equitable and equal mobility environment is one in which all individuals, irrespective of their abilities, can accomplish their daily activities safely, effectively, comfortably and conveniently without being restricted by the poor design, management or maintenance of the local environment (Lahav 2014). The principles of equitable and equal mobility design aim to accommodate the different range of dimensions, bodily shapes and movements, in the confidence that urban designers, planners and manufacturers should ensure that products, services and buildings address the needs of the widest possible population (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002).

4.2.1. Measures to improve sustainable mobility of older people

Although much travel in old age is carried out using a car, walking is still considered one of the most significant travel modes in the local environment. In European cities, 30–50% of older walk. At the same time, falls in the local environment are directly or indirectly caused by barriers within the local environment, thus safety is an important attribute of older people's movements when they go out of their place of residence (Levin et al. 2012). Over 60% of all falls, injuries and accidents among older people outside their place of residency are caused by unaided pedestrians. According to prior studies, these falls, injuries and accidents among older people walking alone are often due to external or environmental and health factors. The findings from prior studies and statistics analysis of accidents in Norway revealed that older pedestrians are at much higher risk of falls and are more vulnerable to accidents and injuries (Elvik and Bjørnskau 2019). They are also faced with more serious and longer-lasting harms when injured, including reduced quality of life and life expectancy (Levin et al. 2012).

Figure 6 depicts the sustainable mobility of older people in the local environment which is based on the mobility needs, requirements and requisites. This is because older people appreciate prepared pedestrian crossings and signal-regulated intersections (Levin et al. 2012). Also, a divided

Figure 6. Sustainable mobility of older people in a local environment.

lane for cyclists and pedestrians is a highly highlighted measure that can make it safer for older people when walking within and across cities. Different lanes can both improve the desire and the ability of older people to walk (Elvik and Bjørnskau 2019). The provision of pedestrianised areas at intersections, warning and guiding information in place before kerbs is important. Also, the removal of steps, introduction of one-way traffic in local streets, widening of pavements and separation of pedestrians and bicyclists' lanes. Besides, filling holes in pavements and provision of more benches in pedestrianised areas can improve the walkability of older people (Levin et al. 2012). The findings from older pedestrians highlighted that walking is an exercise which improves their well-being and welfare, hence stimulating them to be active and participate in society (Krogstad, Hjorthol, and Tennøy 2015). Another highly rated measure is the provision of benches that can be used for resting especially when older people go for walking.

Information availability about local activities for older people was also highlighted as a measure that increases walking among older people since it may help decrease the barriers related to the absence of a walking companion (Krogstad, Hjorthol, and Tennøy 2015). In some European cities, older people stated that improved winter maintenance of roads is one of the most important measures that enhances the walking activities of older people. Krogstad, Hjorthol, and Tennøy (2015) pointed out that most older people opt not to go out walking if winter maintenance is not well provided. Poor winter maintenance is seen as a barrier that limits older people from going out. This is unusually true for older people who are faced with physical mobility issues or feel less safe when walking on icy or slippery surfaces (Elvik and Bjørnskau 2019).

4.2.2. Measures to improve mobility accessibility of older people

Too often mobility equity and equality are not fully considered in public transportation planning, design and implementation in municipalities (Babinard et al. 2012). Accessibility refers to the ease

of reaching different destinations (Alsnih and Hensher 2003). It can also be described as the ease with which residents can move around their local environments to reach destinations, activities, facilities and services, using a preferred mobility mode (by walking, cycling or public transit) and at an ideal time (Wazani, Mohamad, and Jaafar 2021). Accessible mobility requirements of older people, mostly those with disabilities, should be considered by designing and building barrier-free public transportation systems. This necessitates understanding and identifying situations that create barriers for older people (Babinard et al. 2012). Accessibility may enhance perceived quality of life and activity participation, especially for older people with disabilities or impaired mobility. For instance, ramps (curb cuts) can support residents pushing baby strollers, travel information in simple language, provide for non-native speakers and individuals with hearing impairment and regular announcements of each public stop or station to support commuters who are unfamiliar with public transit route and older people with legal blindness/vision impairment (Babinard et al. 2012).

Therefore, improved accessibility and mobility availability are important features in reducing poverty and can enable community participation. Physical accessibility can also benefit individuals who are not disabled but have reduced mobility, including pregnant women, children and older people. Several factors can influence accessibility to infrastructures and facilities in the local environment such as accessible routes, slip resistance and even surface, safer pedestrian crossing, safety from fast traffic and longer green time at traffic lights at pedestrian crossings. As such, it is essential that accessibility planning is integrated into strategic urban development (Sze and Christensen 2017). Quite recently, the accessibility concept has been aligned with the “Universal design” or “Design for all” approach (Wretstrand and Marin-Lamellet 2011), which has supported cities and communities during urban planning and design (Anthony Jnr 2022).

4.3. Universal design for mobility equity and equality of older people

The EU and the USA have proposed several regulations and guidelines to operationalise, design and develop mobility accessibility for people with disabilities and older people with limited mobility (Babinard et al. 2012; Department of Justice 2010; European Commission 2007; United Nations 2008). The policies ban the discrimination of disabled persons and promote free and equal mobility access to everyone in society (Fürst and Vogelauer 2012). Likewise, the principles of the United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CPRD) created a new push which promotes mobility infrastructure and services accessibility (United Nations 2007, 2008, 2012). In the context of this study, *mobility accessibility* refers to older people’s ability to reach activities, services, goods and destinations. Accessibility can also be regarded as the ease of reaching. Thus, for any public transportation system to achieve social inclusion or equity and equality its accessibility must be universal for everyone in society (Abir and Hoque 2011; Chaurasia, Sankat, and Solanki 2017; Fürst and Vogelauer 2012). According to WHO (2011), universal design can be defined as the design of the built environments and societal services that are usable by everyone without the need for constant adaptation.

Therefore, universal design measures or design-for-all have been proposed in urban development (Center for Universal Design 1995; Fürst and Vogelauer 2012). Universal design is a paradigm that emerged from accessible design or barrier-free and assistive technology. It is a social framework for the design of things, places, communication, information and policies that can be usable by a different group of people functioning without separate or special design (Mackett 2020). Over the years, universal design has been employed to build different solutions for products, buildings, transportation, etc. that are effective and usable for everyone, not just older people with disabilities (Abir and Hoque 2011). Universal design principles aim to achieve flexibility in use, equitable use, intuitive and simple use, perceptible information, low physical effort, tolerance for error, size and public space management during land use (Center for Universal Design 1995). Furthermore, universal design focuses on designing and implementing services and facilities that are compatible and useable for individuals whose mobility would have been hindered by physical constraints but are now

able to use public services or facilities, due to the better design and implementation measures (Mackett 2020; Park and Chowdhury 2022).

The universal design concepts provide the design of facilities that fulfils the needs of end users (Vanderschuren, Baufeldt, and Phayane 2015). Hence, it is not on the users of the designed services and facilities to adjust to the built environment but instead that the implemented services and facilities adjust to the needs of the users (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). Universal design proposes to create a local environment that provides better mobility and improved levels of accessibility for persons who would normally experience physical or social barriers (Mackett 2020). Universal design results in better designs that are much more efficient and safe (WHO 2011). Presently, to improve the mobility of the older population, especially older people with disabilities the concept of “universal design”, “design for all” or “inclusive design” is being adopted across cities around the world (Center for Universal Design 1995; Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). Fostering sustainable development by improving the public transportation system is important, especially for older people who make up a large part of the population. Universal design is one of the approaches that if adopted can promote mobility equity and equality for older people towards safe and secure public transportation and walkability within and across cities (Anthony Jnr et al. 2020; Sze and Christensen 2017). Accordingly, Table 3 summarises the universal design principles, description and initiatives to be employed to improve mobility equity and equality for older people in a local environment.

Universal design offers a framework for achieving equal and equitable possibilities for different users in society. Equal mobility opportunity is paramount to physical planning (Levin et al. 2012). In Norway, universal design (universell utforming in Norwegian), has become a well-adopted standard in Norwegian urban planning, management and legislation as it aims for the designing products, environments and services to be usable by all user groups, to the utmost extent possible, without the need for specialised or adaptation design (Miljøverndepartementet 2007). The “Ministry of the Environment” now The “Ministry of Climate and the Environment” in Norway provides guidelines on the characterisation and explanation of the universal design and advocates its adoption as the basis for design and implementation in various sectors. This is because the concept of universal

Table 3. Universal design principles, descriptions and initiatives adapted from Mackett (2020).

Principles	Description	Initiatives
Equitable use	The designed product or service is useful and viable to people with different abilities.	Ease of access starting from entry, to ticketing, towards boarding and departure.
Flexible use	The designed product or service adapts to a wide range of users’ abilities and preferences.	Real-time information, levelled platform with sits/coach, offering flexibility in choice and timing of mobile travel.
Intuitive and simple use	Provision of easy-to-understand designed product or service, irrespective of the user’s language skills, knowledge, experience or current awareness level.	Sensory and spatial information integration at all types of Mass Rapid Transit System (MRTS).
Perceptible information	The designed product or service effectively communicates the needed information to the user, despite the user’s sensory proficiencies or the ambient conditions.	Legible, simplified, easy and alternative information and wayfinding design for a diversity of individuals.
Tolerance for error	The designed product or service reduces risks and the vulnerable consequences of unintended or accidental actions.	Design for people and infrastructure safety at edges such as platforms, corners, staircase nosing, lift controls, structural systems of the train coach or built form, etc.
Low physical effort	The designed product or service can be used comfortably and efficiently and with limited fatigue to users.	Ease in accessible information systems (audio, visual and tactile), vertical mobility, standardisation, coach position, sensory information in ticket vending machines, etc.
Space and size for method and use	Appropriate size and space are provided for use regardless of the user’s posture, body size or mobility.	Provision of edge protection bars around the pathway, aisle gates, coloured warning lines, tactile, etc. for the accommodation of all users.

design offers a new paradigm that incorporates a stronger prominence on equality in relation to improved accessibility for persons with reduced functionality, thus providing products and services that are usable by all people (Miljøverndepartementet 2007). As products and services are designed and deployed in such a way that they can be utilised by individuals of all ages and with diverse skill levels, functionality and ability. Aspects relating to mobility, hearing, vision, sensitivity and comprehension towards the environment (allergies/asthma) are essential in this context (Levin et al. 2012). Overall, the universal design concept offers a promising approach that can be employed for the increased population of older people and the ageing society (Miljøverndepartementet 2007).

4.4. Comparative review of mobility policies for older people with disabilities

The United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CPRD) advocates for strategies that ensure mobility accessibility in existing public transportation services and infrastructures (United Nations 2007). The CRPD highlighted that barriers and obstacles to indoor and outdoor public facilities and urban environments should be removed to provide equal and equitable access to individuals with disabilities, limited mobility and all members of society (United Nations 2005). Mobility exclusion and inequality are often due to vulnerable users' inability to access or use public transportation systems. Thus, accessible, safe and efficient public transportation is a key element of community integration. Therefore, accessible design measures that could address the mobility needs and requirements of all (Shiau and Huang 2014), especially for older people and those with diverse types of disability, including reduced mobility, hearing difficulty and visual impairment could be recommended to municipalities. Disability is associated with individuals having one or more speech difficulties, hearing difficulties, visual impairments and mobility impairments (Sze and Christensen 2017). Mobility restrictions can result in social exclusion which is a situation where certain individuals in the society cannot participate in activities, while they would prefer to do so (Mogaji and Nguyen 2021). Moreover, as pointed out by Sze and Christensen (2017) in the United Kingdom (UK), the percentage of the population older than 65 years of age will increase in the coming years and most older people have some sort of disability which impedes their mobility.

Older people with disabilities are commonly identified as part of this group (which comprises low-income groups, women, minority groups and others), that may be faced with social exclusion as a result of difficulties in using public transport and reduced mobility are among the causes. According to the United Nations, approximately 650 million people or almost 10% of the world's population, have a form of disability (United Nations 2005). Older people with physical disabilities are often faced with challenging obstacles mostly when they travel outdoors. This can prevent them from having access to cultural activities and leisure, visiting public locations, using public transportation and even leaving their place of residence (Mayordomo-Martínez et al. 2019). As such a few mobility policies and strategies have been put forward in different countries to improve the mobility of older people with disabilities, as discussed below.

4.4.1. United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom (UK) "The Inclusive Transport Strategy" by the government to ensure that disabled people are provided with the same access to public transportation as everyone else in society with the capability to confidently travel, easily without any extra costs (Mogaji and Nguyen 2021). This is important as in the UK about 20 per cent of the population are considered to be impaired or disabled in some form, where approximately two-thirds are older than 60 years of age and it was reported that more than half of this population had difficulties daily going out. Further analyses of the figures suggest that two-thirds of disabled older people are over 60 years old, with the majority being female. These findings recommend that a large percentage of the population may presently face difficulty in gaining access to various aspects of the local environment due to the diverse and unseen barriers that impact mobility accessibility within the built environment.

Moreover, in the UK, regulation on disability discrimination was established which requires statutory provision of access to public facilities and buildings for people with disabilities in 1996.

In relation to this, the Department for Transport proposed a complete guideline for the design of accessible transportation facilities. The specified requirements were adopted in the design and operation of the pedestrian environment, public transportation infrastructure and public transportation facilities (Sze and Christensen 2017). The design guidelines suggested by the UK address the mobility needs of people with diverse types of disabilities (as seen in Table 2), including visual and mobility impairment (i.e. individuals using white-tipped canes, wheelchair users and individuals with assistance dogs, etc.) were taken into consideration. These strategies specified minimum and necessary dimensions for facilities and building infrastructures, including ramps, entrances, public access routes, escalators, stairs and lifts, traffic control facilities, including foot-bridge, pedestrian crossings, curbs, and/or underpass and details of bus terminals, bus stops, bus vehicles, rail vehicles and railway platforms (Sze and Christensen 2017).

4.4.2. Canada

In countries such as Canada, about 1 in 4 people will be aged above 65 by 2031 (Statistics Canada 2005). In the transportation sector, "Transport Canada" has been engaged in international dialogue and research, specifically on mobility accessibility (ECMT 2001a). In 2005, the Province of Ontario approved the Accessibility for Ontarians Disability Act (AODA), which aims to develop accessible transportation infrastructure in the province by 2025 that will mainly benefit older people with disability and impairment (Mercado, Páez, and Newbold 2010). Similarly, the federal transport ministry in Canada considers the ageing population as part of its major public transportation challenges (however, this is limited to disability problems) (Government of Canada 2003). The current Ontario's transportation policy statement (unchanged since 2006) is mainly based on facilitating Ontario's goal of building strong communities and a strong economy by enabling the free movement of people and goods across the province through an efficient, safe and integrated multi-modal mobility system (Mercado, Páez, and Newbold 2010).

4.4.3. European countries

The European Conference of Ministers of Transport (ECMT), of which the Scandinavian countries are members, has collaborated with other member states in Europe to improve transportation accessibility towards addressing the needs of an increasing the mobility needs of older people. This is based on a 2001 resolution that established pledges made from 1978 to 1997 for accessible and safe transport and land-use planning (ECMT 2001a) as well as the training and evaluation of drivers (ECMT 2001b), better legislation for improved access to public transportation and monitoring of the adoption of accessibility policies (ECMT 2004; ECMT 2006) and resolving accessibility issues faced by taxi and other dedicated door-to-door mobility service (ECMT 2006). Overall, the ECMT resolutions centred their policy on three key areas which include offering mobility options, ensuring the provision of an accessible environment for urban mobility and institutional and legislative reforms that will address the transport issues faced by older people (Mercado, Páez, and Newbold 2010).

In a Norwegian survey conducted, 15 per cent of participants within the working age identified themselves as having some type of disability. In comparison to the age of participants between 50 and 65 years, 30 per cent identified as having some type of disability (Samfunnsspeilet nr 2004). Addressing mobility access issues for older people with disabilities is not a minimal problem, and it is projected to increase. This current study comprises various modes of public transportation used by older adults to improve their everyday mobility such as the car, public transportation (including specialised or facilitated transit services for older and disabled people), cycling, walking as well as a few other travel modes that are valuable for older people; for example, motorised wheelchairs and mobility scooters (Levin et al. 2012). Therefore, municipalities must be supportive and provide mobility access for all individuals. Therefore, urban planning, design, procedures, practices

and policy should conform to appropriate best practices as guidelines for equitable and inclusive mobility for older adults with disabilities.

4.5. Factors that impact older people mobility

Overall, the mobility needs of older people is complex since it's based on several factors, such as their psychological state, health, physical ability, etc., that may vary not only between age groups but also between persons. This can lead to different modal choices for the same or different individuals which may vary daily (Levin et al. 2012). Over the years, only a few studies have looked into important factors that impact the development and individual use of public transportation systems and community-based forms of transportation (Mercado, Páez, and Newbold 2010). Therefore, there is a need to explore the factors that impact the affordability, appropriateness, easy-to-use, integrated and secure mobility of older people, particularly in regions where public transportation services are limited or inadequate. There is increased awareness that older people with disabilities should be able to accomplish their daily and leisure activities safely, efficiently and enjoyably according to their abilities. Yet, regardless of several government directives and policies on mobility transport accessibility for all, the design of the public transportation infrastructures in a local environment is still lagging (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). Presently, the *design of facilities in public spaces* in the local environment is a barrier to accessibility as many public and commercial structures are still not accessible for disabled older people such as wheelchair users. Also, a few buildings offer signage and mobility aids that assist wayfinding for older people with legal blindness/vision impairment, sensory and learning impairment and most public transportation systems exclude older people with a wide range of learning disabilities (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002). Disabled older people are consequently denied opportunities to manage their lives independently due to the poor design of our cities and urban areas which poses obstacles to them accessing public transportation, suitable housing, public spaces and buildings. Although some areas in the urban space may be considered accessible to older people, the topography of the local environment has resulted in social exclusion and physical inaccessibility for older and disabled people. Therefore, the city's public transportation systems, physical infrastructure and pedestrian realm have thus limited older people with disabilities from participating in the community (Kenyon, Lyons, and Rafferty 2002).

Moreover, the *provision of investments* by the municipalities to improve public transportation should take a long-range view of how the local transit competitiveness could be improved to meet the mobility concerns of an ageing society. Aside from *pricing* and *service frequency* which have been found as factors that influence older peoples' use of public transportation, the *convenience* provided by the local transit as assessed by the *distance to transit stops*, *number of transfers and waiting time* should also be considered as they are issues relevant to the actual travel of older people (Mercado, Páez, and Newbold 2010). The provision of readable travel *information* in a consistent way is important for older people. Since many older people cannot hear or see clearly as good as younger people. Hence, the *information provision* before the trip and during the journey should be audible and visual, timetables should be easy to read by older adults, it should be easy to purchase a ticket and use the ticket machine, low floor vehicles would be required and free seats dedicated for older people, and it is preferable for the city bus driver not to start moving before older passengers are seated (Bokolo, Petersen, and Helfert 2022; Muñoz et al. 2016). However, *inadequate information and knowledge* about public transportation services is often limited among older people, which has resulted in older people travelling less or using public transportation (Levin et al. 2012). Nowadays, much travel information is provided online but most older people do not utilise the internet (Anthony Jnr et al. 2021). Also, most older adults choose to use simple mobile phones that do not access apps or the internet which can provide wayfinding information to older people on a journey (Mackett 2020; Wazani, Mohamad, and Jaafar 2021).

Additionally, it is central to *raise awareness* and promote the adoption of facilitated and specialised mobility transit options among older adults and their families and caregivers (Oxley, Langford, and Charlton 2010). *Information campaigns and awareness* should be provided to which is in line to address older people's travel needs. New methods of providing information using the latest technologies could be adapted to meet the mobility needs of older people. Sometimes, older people lack information during travel but too much of it or the unsuitable kind (Levin et al. 2012; Oxley, Langford, and Charlton 2010). Moreover, the *provision of public transportation facilities*, such as wind shelters, accessible vehicles and plain pavements at bus stops and the provision of information on the available routes and frequency in relation to the mobility needs of older people. Another conclusion is related to the *technological know-how* of older people who are not *experienced in using mobility phones* to manage the booking of their journeys, the complexity associated with using these systems can become a barrier that limits travelling for older people (Levin et al. 2012). Also, issues related to *data privacy and security* via the collection and protection of personal data of older people and improving personal integrity, through increased independence, assurance and autonomy is lacking (Sochor 2015).

5. Discussion and implications

5.1. Discussion

The findings from this study investigate existing works related to mobility equity and equality for older people in a local environment. Moreover, this study explores how universal design measures help to promote mobility equity and equality for inclusive transport systems for older people. Therefore, this study adopts universal design measures to reduce the barriers that impact mobility equity and equality for older people in a local environment. Sze and Christensen 2017 stated that while universal design measures contribute to aiding older people, especially older people with disabilities (physical, in a wheelchair or with legal blindness/vision impairment, sensory and learning impairment), who use public transportation, universal design should not be seen as "technological fixes". Several universal design measures were suggested in the literature such as the deployment of elevated platforms for boarding and departing from city buses, a decrease in level difference at pavement/curbside and a decrease in gap size between bus/rail transit vehicles and platforms to improve accessibility (Anthony and Petersen 2020; Sze and Christensen 2017).

Presently, the use of conventional public transportation is generally quite low among older people (Sochor 2015). As such, mobility equity and equality measures are deemed necessary if the older population's travel needs and requirements are to be met. Levin et al. (2012) revealed that the use of public transportation among older people can increase in local environments where specific measures (such as, service buses, flexible mobility service, community transportation, etc.) have been deployed to address the needs of the older population (Pinto et al. 2020). Conversely, the results from some studies showed that regardless of such accessibility measures, older people's use of public transportation is still lower than expected. Sze and Christensen (2017) stated that to improve the mobility of older people with auditory and visual impairment, route guidance and recommendations with contrasting colour tactile markers for accessible paths to public transportation facilities and particularly with clear signs of the position of platform, entrance, bus stop and vehicle were effective and useful in improving mobility safety and accessibility. Audio information regarding the arrival of public vehicles can also improve the perceived service level for the use of public transportation.

Accordingly, further findings from this study identify factors that influence older people's mobility, especially those with disabilities in a local environment. Park and Chowdhury (2018) highlighted addressing the mobility needs of older people with disabilities and inclusion into society are some of the basic human needs as people with disabilities are seen as vulnerable groups in the community. Understanding their needs will make them feel less isolated and more included in the community.

Municipalities are encouraged to interact, co-create and co-design with the disability communities to understand their mobility requirements and needs, especially when implementing public transportation infrastructures (Park and Chowdhury 2018). Moreover, large and clear signage and timetables in largely displayed that are legible to older people with impaired vision are required. In general, improved access to public transportation may reduce the level of mobility exclusion and mobility equity for older people in a local environment while increasing mobility and equality and thus improve the perceived quality of life of the older people (Meerow, Pajouhesh, and Miller 2019; Sze and Christensen 2017).

5.2. Implications for theory and policies

The findings from this study provide implications towards mobility challenges faced by vulnerable groups in society mainly older people and those with disabilities towards achieving more inclusive cities, with regulations and policies that allow municipalities to move towards the guarantee of justice, equity and equality in public transportation. More importantly, the findings are expected to better inform policymakers, decision-makers, transport planners and practitioners on how they can improve mobility equity, equality and inclusiveness in a local environment. Potential measures to address the inequitable public transportation in a local environment could include urban policies on the re-design of public vehicles, such as city buses to age and disability-friendly design models. Prioritising strategies to promote inclusive and safe public transportation in municipalities is important in achieving sustainable and accessible mobility facilities for vulnerable road users in society. Furthermore, to improve the legislative perspectives towards mobility equity and equality for older people, institutional cooperation and awareness of government directives in public transportation planning are essential for improving the pedestrian and walking environment and mobility accessibility of public transportation services and facilities. Policies should be directed to the journey time of the older population with disability by substantially improving the accessible design of public transportation infrastructure such as the vehicles, terminals, facilities and interchanges.

5.3. Implications for practice and society

Accordingly, the findings from this study advocate for the provision of equitable and equal access to public transportation for older people as a key policy area that contributes to addressing the mobility needs of the heterogeneous older population. Moreover, the findings from this study offer evidence to decision-makers by providing a deeper insight into how trips are made by older people especially those with disabilities. As pointed out in the literature (Campisi et al. 2021; Vijaya Prakash and Taduri 2020), urban planning and design of public spaces should consider the beginning, the needs of older adults and also respond to the mobility difficulties and requirements faced by older people with physical, visual and hearing disabilities, so that they learn and adapt to move independently to access public services. This study further explores the inclusion of older pedestrians; thus, the pedestrian environment should be based on universal design with walking facilities and the provision of wayfinding information, to promote safe mobility and walkability of older citizens. Hence, this study advocates for local authorities and municipality authorities to re-design pedestrians or walkway networks in close collaboration with older people in the society.

6. Conclusion

This study concludes by speculating that universal design could contribute to providing a more inclusive approach to the re-design of public transportation infrastructure. The findings of this study provide discussion on the background of older people's mobility, the accessible mobility perspective of older people with disabilities and social equity and equality for the mobility of older people. The findings also provide social and non-social design principles, walkability and wayfinding

issues faced by older people and measures to improve mobility accessibility and sustainable mobility of older people. Lastly, the findings provide a discussion on how universal design can be employed for mobility equity and equality of older people and then a comparative finding of mobility policies for older people with disabilities is presented. More importantly, the findings from this article present factors that influence the local environment in achieving mobility equity and equality from the perspectives of older people living without and with disabilities (physical, in a wheelchair or with legal blindness/vision impairment, sensory and learning impairment).

Further findings from this study propose guidelines to help municipalities develop mobility equity and equality for older people based on a set of recommendations provided to inform urban transport policies on universal accessibility. This study opted to employ universal design in the local environment as it can help to remove the hindrances and barriers faced by older people and those with disabilities in performing their everyday activities. The findings from this study go beyond the existing literature by proposing the adoption of universal design measures help to promote mobility equity, equality and accessibility for inclusive urban transport systems for older people, thereby increasing the autonomy and independence, of older people in society. Overall, the findings from this study are based on a systematic literature review and only secondary data were collected from the literature. Future work will collect primary data using interviews and focus group workshops from older people representative groups to provide more insights on how equity, equality and accessibility for older people in the local environment can be improved towards sustainable public transportation.

Acknowledgments

Open access funding facilitated by Østfold University College, Halden, Norway.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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